
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND MARKETING PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SCALE ENTERPRISES IN UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

This study was designed to examine the influence of digital transformation on the marketing performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. It specifically sought to unravel the effect of digital transformation on sales volume and customer satisfaction. To do this, the researchers used a cross-sectional research design that let them get firsthand information from 312 SME owners operating in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State at one point in time using a well-structured questionnaire. We descriptively analysed the obtained data and tested the formulated hypotheses using simple linear regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed that digital transformation had a significant positive influence on sales volume, customer satisfaction, and the overall marketing performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. On the basis of these findings, we recommended that SMEs consistently utilise and integrate digital technology in their daily operations by ensuring the use of digital platforms to personalise their marketing messages. A conclusion and suggested areas for further studies were made.

Keywords: Digital transformation, Marketing performance, SMEs, Customer satisfaction

Introduction

The advent of digital technology has created new business opportunities for economic growth on a global scale. There is a widespread agreement among business researchers that digital transformation has the ability to boost trade and economic growth, as well as reduce global inequality among developed economies and developing nations (Wadhwa and Grover, 2023). Digital transformation has emerged as a vital and essential component of both traditional and contemporary marketing, enabling companies to improve customer experiences, boost sales growth, and capitalise on competitive advantages in the current digital landscape (Nwaogu, 2023). However, this concept has received considerable attention in academic circles for the past two to three decades, but it's only been in the last few years that businesses have begun to put this theory into action (Popović-Pantić *et al.*, 2019).

“Digital transformation” is gaining more and more attention not just because it is a worldwide trend but also because this concept offers tangible benefits to business environment as a whole (Wang and Yan, 2023). The concept refers to the process of improving and re-creating conventional marketing strategies using digital technologies (Joel *et al.*, 2024). Digital transformation primarily entails reforming an organisation and its internal mechanisms in order to introduce a novel approach to products, consumers, or services. It occurs when businesses leverage technology across social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, and departments to significantly enhance the quality of customer services (Etuk *et al.*, 2021). Digital transformation involves merely enhancing the efficiency or effectiveness of current processes with modern technologies.

In order for small businesses to undergo digital transformation, they must implement new technologies that alter their core business model as well as their goods, services, and procedures. The performance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) is critical in economic development. SMEs are the backbone of any growing economy, driving both economic progress and fair growth. SMEs are defined as businesses with fewer than a certain number of employees (Etuk *et al.*, 2021). Studies have shown that small and medium-scale enterprises are actively seeking to establish dominance in the digital space (Ziółkowska, 2021). These SMEs are developing a technological approach that distinguishes them from their rivals and provides them with a competitive advantage in attaining performance (Usani *et al.*, 2024).

Gaining insight into how small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) successfully manage and thrive in challenging situations is essential for their long-term viability and important for the overall economic environment (Shee and Kaswi, 2023). The resilience of SMEs to sustain operations, retain their personnel, and continue making economic contributions despite disruptions caused by crises, as well as the high cost of raw materials for production, highlights their significance as dynamic drivers of economic growth and employment generation (Etuk *et al.*, 2024; Usani *et al.*, 2024). SMEs play a crucial role in job creation, fostering economic expansion, and providing assistance to local communities (Ebitu, *et al.*, 2015).

Marketing performance denotes the process of assessing how well an organisation's marketing efforts contribute to achieving its objectives (Hamid *et al.*, 2022). The notion refers to the efficacy with which a business promotes its goods and services. Marketing performance is the end result of a company's strategy implementation, and it includes metrics like consumer satisfaction, customer retention, sales growth, sales volume, profitability, productivity, and the success of new products. Measuring marketing performance is critical

for small and medium-scale businesses, as it serves as a benchmark for judging and comparing their marketing initiatives (Hawa *et al.*, 2023). However, past researches suggest that businesses that do not adopt digital transformation are at risk of lagging behind competitors who are using digital technologies to gain a competitive edge (Ning and Yeo, 2023).

In today's digital marketplace, organisations are customising customer relationships, implementing micromarketing strategies in campaigns for targeted groups, and providing consistent omnichannel experiences to drive innovation (Etuk *et al.*, 2021). Enterprises need to leverage digital platforms to improve communication with their suppliers, customers, and competitors. In light of the ever-changing digital landscape and the myriad of external environmental factors impacting the performance of SMEs in Nigeria, it is imperative that businesses prioritise the development of marketing strategies that are both robust and sustainable while making full use of digital technologies. It has been observed that many SMEs fail to recognise these opportunities and instead struggle to evaluate the consequences of digitalisation in order to determine what they can digitise and which platforms are appropriate for sales activities (Pfister and Lehmann, 2023).

This suggests that SMEs require additional guidance on how their management may become digitally literate and adaptable (Neumeyer *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, there is a lack of literature on the effects of digitalisation and very rudimentary studies on how SMEs might effectively digitalise their operations. This study aims to fill this gap in the literature by investigating the influence of digital transformation on the marketing performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. In light of this interest, the specific objectives of this study are as follows:

- i. To investigate how digital transformation affects the sales volume of SMEs
- ii. Examine how digital transformation influences customer satisfaction.

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Digital Transformation

Digital transformation places a greater emphasis on the technological underpinnings of information technology and the integration of business models (Kaoud and El Dine, 2022). One definition of digital transformation is the process by which a company changes its business activities to make better use of computing, communication, and connection in order to increase its performance (Mangifera and Mawardi, 2022). Digital transformation refers to the process by which a company undergoes the necessary modifications to incorporate digital technologies. These technologies include moving data storage to the cloud and utilising email, office software, and social networks. Napate *et al.* (2020) state that digital transformation involves the ways in which digital technology can alter business models, leading to new products, different organisational settings, or the computerisation of previously manual activities. In marketing, it encompasses the use of advanced technologies like cloud computing, big data analytics devices, social media platforms artificial intelligence (AI), and the internet of things (IoT) to foster creativity to enhance marketing performance.

Marketing Performance

The growing interest in online media has created shifts that have prompted new approaches to doing business. Although numerous technologies enable SMEs to enhance their current workflows, they can also empower sales representatives to deliver value in novel ways, such as by digitalising customer-relationship processes to enhance productivity or performance. According to Gakii and Maina (2019), marketing performance is when companies use their limited resources to satisfy customer demand and achieve market-related objectives, such as increasing sales, profit, and market share. Usani *et al.* (2021), Etuk *et al.* (2021), Etuk *et al.* (2024), and Usani *et al.* (2024) have shown that market share, total sales, customer happiness, and client acquisition are the key performance indicators in the market. Businesses can gain an advantage over their competitors and even outmanoeuvre them by measuring marketing success and adjusting their strategy accordingly (Usani *et al.*, 2021). The following section discusses the marketing performance proxies used in this study.

Underpinnings of Marketing Performance

Sales Volume

Sales volume refers to the total amount of money or sales transaction conducted by a business organisation within a given time frame (Uwasomba and Boniface, 2023). The sales volume is calculated by multiplying the number of units sold by the prices of the commodities sold. Some researchers assert that the customer patronage through spending and satisfaction generates sales volume that can be measured in various units such as litres, cartons, cans, or in monetary terms like naira and dollar (Etuk *et al.* 2021; Uwasomba and Boniface, 2023). While some researchers believe that digital transformation have positive effect on sales volume (Smith 2024; Etuk *et al.*, 2022). Pierre *et al.* (2022) confirm that there is positive significant relationship between digital technology and sales volume of big and small firms. Moreover, (Wayne, 2002) found a link between sales promotion dimensions and product trial which eventually lead to increase in sales volume. (Pauwels *et al.*, 2002) also discovered that sales promotion dimensions have permanent effect on sales volume.

Customer Satisfaction

The ability to keep customers satisfied has been one of the most important factors in a company's success. A higher rate of customer satisfaction directly correlates to higher profits for the business. No matter the product or service, the most crucial component is making sure the customer is satisfied (Usani *et al.*, 2021). Customer happiness, according to Etuk *et al.* (2022), is a sign that a company's offerings are up to par with or better than what the market demands. According to Usani and Sampson (2023), the term "customer satisfaction" refers to the emotional state a person experiences as a result of evaluating the actual performance of a product in relation to their expectations. According to Onyia *et al.* (2024), a customer's level of satisfaction can be described as the degree to which their expectations were met or exceeded, as measured by how happy or disappointed they were. Customers who are satisfied with organisation services are more likely to return and buy more, which boosts performance.

Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria

The success of SMEs is seen as crucial to Nigeria's economic development. Ediri (2014) asserts that SMEs in Nigeria have been the driving force behind economic growth due

to the growth potential they offer, the vital roles they play in the manufacturing and value chains, and the multiplier impacts they have on the rest of the economy. There will be more jobs, less poverty, more wealth, more equitable income distribution, and less income disparity in the nation because of the small and medium enterprise sector. When it comes to economic modernisation and growth in Nigeria, the small and medium enterprise (SME) sector is at the forefront. There needs to be proper consideration of this vital sector in Nigerian policymaking and program implementation.

According to Siti *et al.* (2014), Nigeria boasts Africa's largest economy. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of any economy, as pointed out by these writers. Given the many benefits that result from encouraging such businesses in developing nations like Nigeria's—including more equitable distribution of income and wealth, greater economic autonomy, the growth of new businesses, job opportunities, and more—it's obvious that doing so is crucial. But existing research on small and medium-sized businesses in developing nations, like Nigeria, shows that they haven't lived up to the country's expectations (Siti *et al.*, 2014).

Based on the existing reviewed literature, this study adopts sales volume and customer satisfaction as dimensions of marketing performance, while maintaining digital transformation as a uni-dimensional construct. This study assumes that digital transformation has an impact on marketing performance. However, the researchers developed a conceptual framework in figure 2.1 to illustrate the relationship between the variables under study.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework on Digital Transformation and Marketing Performance of SMEs. Source: Researchers Model (2024).

Theoretical Framework

The process of digital transformation requires strategic frameworks due to its complexity and scope. In order to help businesses, especially SMEs, navigate the digital landscape, researchers have created a number of frameworks to better understand, plan, and execute their business strategy (Unegbu *et al.*, 2024; Lottu *et al.*, 2023). The theoretical foundation for this study is the technology-organisation-environment (TOE) model, which was proposed in 1990 by Mitchell Fleischer and Louis G. Tornatzky. The theory delves at the relationship between technology, the organisation, and the ecosystem. It highlights how these three elements impact a company's attempts to innovate and adopt new technologies. The TOE framework, when applied to the context of digital transformation, emphasises how the internal culture, structure, and external market conditions of an organisation can influence the successful application of digital technology (Li, Long, and Zhao, 2022). This theory is applicable to the research at hand because it suggests that businesses, especially SMEs, should evaluate the interoperability of these parts and pinpoint any potential problem areas that can hinder the smooth incorporation of digital technology in their operation.

Empirical Literature

Nwaogu (2023) examined the impact of digital transformation on marketing operations in SMEs located in Owerri, Imo State. The study employed a descriptive research design. The main data were gathered using a questionnaire. The study selected a sample of 50 small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The research used regression analysis and discovered strong links between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Findings show that the implementation of digital transformation has a substantial impact on the business performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Sidabutar and Siswanto (2024) conducted a recent study on the impact of digital transformation on the performance of SMEs in the food and beverage industry in Indonesia. The researchers employed a quantitative descriptive strategy, utilising a questionnaire to collect primary data. The collected data was analysed using a structural equation model (SEM), and their findings revealed that there is a direct correlation between digital transformation and the performance of SMEs.

In their study, Hawa *et al.* (2023) investigated the impact of digital transformation on the marketing performance of bird cage craftsmen in Ajibarang. The researchers used a sample of 97 participants, selected by purposive sampling technique. The research conducted using Smart PLS indicates that digital transformation has a beneficial impact on marketing performance. Hokonya (2015) conducted a mixed research approach on digital transformation and customer satisfaction in a standard chartered bank in Zimbabwe. A semi-structured questionnaire was employed to gather data from both the customer and employees. Data analysis was then done employing both qualitative and quantitative techniques using thematic analysis of interview sheets. According to the results, the investigated bank's digital transformation journey was a resounding success, much to the delight of workers and customers alike.

In their study, Mangifera and Mawardi (2022) investigated the key elements that drive digital transformation in small food and beverage firms, with the goal of enhancing their financial performance amid the COVID-19 epidemic. The researchers employed a quantitative research methodology, utilising a sample size of 104 individuals involved in small business operations. The data obtained was analysed using Smart PLS 3.0. The findings demonstrated a significant influence of digital transformation on the financial performance of small food and beverage enterprises in Surakarta. Luo (2023) looked at a subset of Chinese A-share businesses that went public between 2012 and 2022 to see how digital transformation affected their bottom lines. The overarching goal was to mitigate the impact of environmentally friendly technical advancements. The research was descriptive in character, and it relied on a questionnaire design to collect data from its subjects. To examine whether there is a connection between digital transformation and company success, the benchmark regression analysis was employed. The results show that digital transformation is a driver of green technology innovation and firm performance.

Unegbu *et al.* (2024) examined the effects of digital transformation on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria, providing an in-depth examination of how digitalisation affects SMEs' competitiveness, operations, and related difficulties. The researchers used a quantitative research approach. The researchers used a structured questionnaire and a stratified sampling technique to collect data from 600 SMEs. The research demonstrates a significant relationship between digital transformation and the competitiveness of SMEs. Nguyen *et al.* (2023) conducted a study in Vietnam to explore the

role of digital transformation in SMEs. The study selected 306 SMEs as its sample. The findings from the study indicated that digital transformation had a positive impact on the business performance of SMEs in Vietnam.

Research Gap

The analysis of the available literature has revealed various research gaps, necessitating urgent investigation into the relationship between digital transformation and the marketing performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Despite the fact that the literature offers insightful perspectives, there are a few areas that need further exploration. There are a few studies that investigate the impact that digital transformation has on particular aspects of performance, such as sales volume, customer retention, cost efficiency, and market growth (Zhang and Li, 2020). However, there is a dearth of holistic models that incorporate these various dimensions in order to provide a complete comprehension of how digital transformation affects the overall marketing performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Future research on digital transformation could focus on developing integrated frameworks that better reflect the multi-dimensional nature of performance. The existence of these research gaps highlights the need for further investigation and emphasises the importance of addressing the complexities and subtleties associated with digital transformation in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Hence, this study delves into these topics to greatly enhance our understanding of how SMEs can leverage digital transformation to achieve long-term success in the Nigerian business environment. To fill the study gap, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of digital transformation on sales volume

H₀₂: Digital transformation does not enhance customer satisfaction

Methodology

The researchers employed a cross-sectional survey approach due to its quantitative nature. This design permits the simultaneous gathering of information from a large number of subjects. Additionally, it enables the researchers to monitor variables without exerting any influence on them. The study area was Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study included all registered firms and operational SMEs involved in the provision of tangible products and services, totalling 447,903. Given the known population, Taro Yamani was employed to ascertain the appropriate sample size of 400. The simple random method of sampling was used in administering a questionnaire to operators of SMEs in various businesses that carry on operations in Akwa Ibom State. This approach provided equal opportunities for all potential research participants to provide information relevant to the study. Data for the study was collected from primary source through the use of a questionnaire.

The questionnaire was self-administered and included two sections. The initial section of the questionnaire was specifically crafted to obtain answers that corresponded to the demographic attributes of the participants. The second component involved gathering data on digital transformation and marketing performance among small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). We assessed the instrument using a 5-point Likert scale to measure the degree of agreement, disagreement, or uncertainty with the statement. The scale runs as follows: strongly agree (5), agree (4), undecided (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). This

instrument allows for cost-effective interaction with a large portion of the population. It provides firsthand information and is simple to administer.

In order to establish the reliability of the questionnaire used, Cronbach's alpha was used in testing the instrument. The test analysis yielded an overall result of 0.760. The coefficient alphas for all proxies adopted for this study are presented in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Reliability Table

Variable	Number of Items	(Cronbach Alpha)
Sales Volume	4	0.771
Customer Satisfaction	4	0.735
Marketing Performance	4	0.826
Overall	12	0.760

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

The reliability outcome showed a high value above 0.70, indicating that the instrument's reliability was suitable for this study. Percentage method and mean were used in analyzing descriptive statistics. Furthermore, in the test of hypotheses, simple regression analysis was used to test hypotheses one and two at a threshold of 0.05

Data Presentation

400 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to SMEs operating in Akwa Ibom State. Out of the 400 copies administered, only 312, constituting 97.99%, were retrieved in usable form. The remaining 88 copies, which made up 2.01%, were incompletely completed. Hence, they were excluded from analysis. We analysed the responses using a statistical package for social science.

Test of Hypotheses
Test of hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of digital transformation on sales volume of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.1: Regression Analysis Result on the influence of digital transformation on Sales volume of small and medium scale enterprises in Akwa Ibom State

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.611 ^a	.373	.336	2.10433		
Goodness of Fit ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	166.393	1	3592.122	11.826	.001 ^b
	Residual	285.323	310	114.253		
	Total	451.716	311			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.319	.147		3.621	.002
	Digital transformation	.396	.163	.413	2.429	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Digital transformation

b. Dependent Variable: Sales volume of SMEs

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024).

Table 4.1 shows the result of a regression analysis on the influence of digital transformation on the sales volume of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. The analysis at $R = .611$ indicates a positive relationship between digital transformation and SMEs' sales volume. The generalised model summary showed an adjusted R^2 of 0.336. This implies that the changes in digital transformation explain 33.6% of the changes in the sales volume of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. The model also showed a goodness of fit of 95 percent (p -value < 0.05). The influence of digital transformation on the sales volume of SMEs was statistically significant at 95% (also p -value < 0.05). This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which posited no significant influence of digital transformation on the sales volume of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, we can assert that digital transformation significantly impacts the sales volume of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. The implication of this result is that digital transformation, when applied effectively as a marketing tool, can enhance the sales volume of SMEs and large businesses.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Digital transformation does not enhance customer satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.2: Regression Analysis Result on the influence of digital transformation on customer satisfaction of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.609 ^a	.371	.334	0.94737		
Goodness of Fit ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	197.104	1	12418.517	177.336	.000 ^b
	Residual	268.213	310	143.251		
	Total	465.317	311			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.026	.329		1.032	4.137
	Digital transformation	.207	.063	.311	3.286	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction of SMEs

b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital transformation

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024).

Table 4.2 shows the results of the regression analysis on the influence of digital transformation on customer satisfaction of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. The analysis R=.609 indicates a positive relationship between digital transformation and customer satisfaction in SMEs. The generalised model summary showed an adjusted R² of 0.334. This implies that the changes in digital transformation influence 33.4% of the changes in customer satisfaction for small and medium-scale enterprises in Akwa Ibom State. The model also showed a goodness of fit of 95 percent (p-value <0.05). The relationship between digital transformation and customer satisfaction in SMEs was statistically significant at 95% (also p-value <0.05). This result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which suggested that digital transformation does not improve customer satisfaction in small and medium-sized enterprises in Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, we can conclude that digital transformation improves the customer satisfaction of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. This result implies that digital transformation can influence the customer satisfaction of SMEs and other businesses.

Discussion of Findings

The main goal of this study was to investigate the influence of digital transformation and marketing performance on SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. Findings of the study revealed that there is a significant influence of digital transformation and the underpinnings of marketing performance (sales volume and customer satisfaction) of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State, as evidenced by their positive standardised regression coefficients (β) and p-values less than 0.05. The first hypothesis resulted in a significant positive influence of digital transformation and sales volume, with a regression coefficient of 0.396. This finding corroborates with Nwaogu (2023); Mangifera and Mawardi (2022); Sidabutar and Siswanto (2024); and Hawa *et al.* (2023), who, in their findings at different locations and times, discovered that digital transformation had a significant positive relationship with marketing performance dimensions like sales volume and profitability.

The second objective was to examine how digital transformation influences customer satisfaction for SMEs. It was hypothesised that digital transformation does not enhance customer satisfaction of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. The test of hypothesis two indicated that digital transformation significantly enhanced customer satisfaction among SMEs in Akwa Ibom State. This outcome strengthens earlier reports by Hokonya (2015); Unegbu *et al.* (2024); Nguyen *et al.* (2023); and Luo (2023), who also found a strong link between excellent digital services and customer satisfaction.

Conclusion and Suggestion for Further Study

The aim of this research was to investigate the influence of digital transformation on the marketing performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study adopted two proxies of marketing performance (sales volume and customer satisfaction) and treated the independent variable (digital transformation) as a uni-dimensional construct. We collected 312 responses, and at the end of the result analysis, it was evidence that digital transformation has a significant positive influence on the two dimensions of marketing performance. These empirical results clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of digital technology as a vital tool for improving firms' marketing performance.

Despite the fact that none of our study's findings contradicted those of previous studies, they still present a promising avenue for future research, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of digital transformation, its various dimensions, and its impact on marketing performance in large firms and other service sectors. Furthermore, we restricted our study to a single state in Nigeria, but we urge future researchers to broaden their geographical scope to see if their findings align with ours.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following suggestions were made:

- i. To enhance sales volume, SMEs should consistently utilise and integrate digital technology in their daily operations by ensuring the use of digital platforms to personalise their marketing messages. This approach can significantly boost sales growth and create new business opportunities.
- ii. To improve customer satisfaction, companies (SMEs) should increase their use of digital platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, TikTok, and Instagram to

broaden their perspective on their customers' needs and expectations in order to meet customer demands and achieve satisfaction through customisation.

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